

Pauline Epistles

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The Pauline epistles refer to the seven authentic Pauline letters: Romans, 1 and 2 Corinthians, Galatians, Philippians, 1 Thessalonians, and Philemon. Even though 13 letters in the New Testament are attributed to Paul these seven are widely regarded to have Paul as their author (in addition to the seven authentic letters, Ephesians, Colossians, 2 Thessalonians, 1 and 2 Timothy, and Titus are attributed to Paul). The Pauline epistles, written approx. 50–62 CE, cover an array of topics, from grand theological/philosophical questions to concrete, on-the-ground issues that arose in the Christ groups. It is important to note that even though later Christianity has based much of its theology in Paul's letters (for example, Martin Luther's famous "justification by faith" comes from Romans 1:17), the letters are incidental and written to specific assemblies at a specific point in time. For example, Paul only mentions the celebration of the "Lord's supper" in 1 Corinthians 11 because the Christ followers in Corinth celebrated the ritual in a faulty manner, according to the apostle. A further point about the Pauline epistles is that many (if not all) of them are primarily addressed to gentile Christ followers and that the topics Paul covers in his letters mainly concern gentiles in-Christ and how they should live. Both during his own time and after his death, Paul left a significant mark on the growing Jesus movement, and later the established church. This can be seen in a number of ways. First, the five letters that are not regarded by scholars as authentic (i.e., Paul did not write them even though they are attributed to him) show the importance in having Paul as the (claimed) author to a text in the early Jesus movement. Second, 2 Peter 3:15–16 explicitly mentions Paul and how his writings can be hard to understand. Third, as Paul's letters make up a considerable part of the New Testament (especially if one counts all 13 letters that are attributed to him), his texts were viewed as important documents by the early Jesus movement when it started to form its canon and decided which texts were foundational for the life of the emerging church. The Pauline epistles have been read, studied, and influential since they were first written, and they continue to be so today. Gaining a deeper understanding of this letter collection helps us better understand the origins of what today is Christianity, Jewish Christian relations in the first century CE, and the ideas that exists in one of the most influential textual corpora in the modern West.

Date Range: 50 CE - 62 CE

Region: Asia Minor

Region tags: Asia Minor

Where Pauline Christ groups were located approx. 50-62 CE

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: E. P. Sanders, Paul: A Very Short Introduction (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001)
- Source 2: Charles B. Puskas and Mark Reasoner, The Letters of Paul: An Introduction (Minnesota: Liturgical

Press, 2013 [2nd ed.]

– Source 3: Mark D. Nanos and Magnus Zetterholm, eds., *Paul within Judaism: Restoring the First-Century Context to the Apostle* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2015)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.biblegateway.com>

– Source 1 Description: Contains all Pauline epistles in translation

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/home/>

– Source 2 Description: Contains all Pauline epistles in their original language (Greek)

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.bibleodyssey.org>

– Source 3 Description: Contains short, easy-to-read articles on biblical topics, including Paul

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: There is no indications that Paul or his scribe(s) would have modified the papyrus in any way prior to writing.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: It is not exactly clear how Paul "wrote" his letters or how long it took. However, we know that he did not write them himself but used a scribe (1 Corinthians 16:21).

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: Many of Paul's letters were copied and circulated. There is no indication that they were stored in specific locations.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The money for the material to write letters most likely came from various Christ groups.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: Since copying a text in antiquity was an expensive task that also required someone who could read and write, it is likely that some of the things Paul wrote were memorized by his audience and by those who delivered and read his letters. However, it is unclear to which degree people memorized Pauline writings.

Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Notes: There is no one story per se that details the origins of scripture. However, Paul, like many other Jews, thought that God had revealed himself to his people and that this, when written down, laid the foundation for what later became the Jewish scriptures.

Revealed by a high god?

– No

Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

Notes: Paul believed that the letters he wrote were indeed partly inspired by the god of Israel or the Lord Jesus Christ (1 Cor 7:10).

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Since the Pauline epistles are holy text to the Church, the Church(es) interpret the apostle's letters. However, this does not mean that all Christians agree on the interpretation on the Pauline epistles (or even which ones in the Church should interpret them).

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

Notes: Depending on the denomination, interpretations can take place in various levels of church authorities. For example, Roman-Catholic churches have a more hierarchical tradition of interpretation where the clergy have more power when it comes to interpretation of scripture than do the lay people. In other churches, mainly protestant ones, interpretation can take place in various levels of the church and they tend to have a more egalitarian approach where interpretation is shared more widely.

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

Notes: One common disagreement is on the leadership of women. Some churches

maintain that women and men have equal right to practice leadership in the church; other churches hold that church leadership is something that should be appointed to only men. One text from the Pauline epistles that is used in this discussion is 1 Cor 14:33-36. Even though there are some textual question marks over this texts, and more general questions about the meaning of Paul's words, some take this text to indicate that women should not hold leadership within the church (at least not ordained leadership or leadership in the services).

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

Notes: In some churches only men are allowed to transmit and/or interpret scriptures

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– Yes

Notes: In some churches only elders or those who have gone through certain education are allowed to transmit and/or interpret scriptures

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: The Pauline epistles are written in what is called koinē Greek, which was a common language in

Paul's day. So, the language per se is not different than "secular" language. However, the way Paul express himself clearly shows that he is writing to "religious" settings.

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Paul used terminology that was in use by other Jewish authors at the time but he also developed a distinct terminology for his Christ followers, often referring to them as "brothers," "sisters," "holy ones," or "chosen ones."

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Notes: All Pauline epistles are written in koinē Greek.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: Unknown

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– I don't know

Notes: It is unknown how many in any given Christ group knew how to read and write.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard, almost impossible, to give an exact number of how many would have listened to Paul's letters. Scholars vary greatly in their suggestions about how many Christ followers each assembly hosted. However, it is probably better to think of smaller numbers (approx. 10-30) since ancient associations seldom were much larger than this.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: Paul does not tell his Christ followers that they must seek to recruit others. However, he does encourage them to live in such a way that they become good examples for others and to spread the message about Jesus Christ.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The Pauline epistles do not deal specifically with religious professionals outside the Jesus movement. However, we can assume that Paul would have wanted these people to become adherents to the Jesus movement just like any other person.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: Those Paul recruited to the Jesus movement were mainly gentiles (i.e., non-Jews) and Paul tells these gentiles that they must abandon their old way of life; in particular, they must not worship their old gods and/or idols anymore. Instead, they can only worship the god of Israel and only recognize Jesus Christ as their Lord. In terms of ritual practices, the initiation rite of the Jesus movement was water immersion (=baptism) and they celebrated a common meal as a sign of their adherence to Christ.

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Even though the term "religious professionals" might not be applicable to Paul and the other apostles in the same sense as to the deacons/priests/bishops in the later

church, it is clear that the apostles (including Paul) spread their message to several different geographical areas. It was their job to travel and spread the news that God had sent his Messiah to the earth and that time was drawing to a close.

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: Paul encourages all Christ followers to spread the word of God and his Messiah. However, this does not mean that he tells all his Christ followers to travel and preach, but they can spread Paul's message in their own cities and by living a life worthy of Paul's message.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Paul tells his Christ followers that they should live as good, visible examples of the faith in Christ Paul proclaims.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: At times, Paul seeks to convince his Christ followers that his interpretation of God and Jesus is the correct one (see the Letter to the Galatians). Paul's seems to envision to types of peoples he wants to counter. The first are those Jews and gentiles who are not convinced that Jesus is the messiah. The second are those who, like Paul, think of Jesus as the messiah but do not agree with Paul on how gentile Christ followers should live their new life as members of the Jesus movement. Basically, what Paul is arguing with regards to gentiles-in-Christ (Paul very rarely talks about Jewish Christ followers since he views himself as sent to the gentiles) is that they have to abandon some parts of their previous life (most notably idol worship and worship of gods other than the god of Israel) and adopt some of the (Jewish) practices of the Jesus movement. However, Paul did not want his gentile Christ followers to

become fully Jewish by adopting the whole of the Jewish law (e.g., Paul tells the males not to circumcise). In this sense, Paul envisions a liminal space for this gentiles-in-Christ where they are to give up many of their previous gentile practices in favour for those of the Jewish Jesus movement, without letting them become fully Jewish.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: Even though we do not know if Paul's letters as such were actually used during any ritual practices in Christ groups, Paul does mention some rituals his Christ followers are to practice. For example, Paul mentions the initiation rite of water immersion (=baptism), the Lord's Supper that is shared among Christ followers, and more generally he gives instructions on how the Christ groups should behave and organize themselves when they meet (which they do regularly).

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: There are several textual witnesses of the Pauline epistles and no one Greek text contains all Pauline epistles. The Greek text one finds in modern versions of the New Testament, and which translations are based on, is a collection of various ancient textual witnesses.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: The most reliable textual witnesses to the Pauline epistles come from the first centuries CE

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: Not all textual witnesses read exactly the same. The differences vary from the placement of certain words to larger variations where one textual witness may have a very different text from another witness.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

Notes: There is a critical apparatus in modern versions of the New Testament in its original language. In this, the editors of any given edition of the Greek New Testament will show what other textual witnesses have as their text and give information about which textual witnesses have which reading. The most plausible reading (according to the modern editors) is given in the main text.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: Even though Paul's letters were not viewed as "Scripture" initially since they were letters sent to various Christ groups, they later became part of the Christian New Testament.

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The canonization of the New Testament was likely established sometime in the third century CE.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: Today, the canon various churches and traditions use are more or less set. However, different churches have different canons and view some of the texts in the New Testament differently. With that said, the Pauline epistles are a stable part of most, if not all, Christian canons due to their early date and authoritative nature in the early church.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: The Pauline epistles are some of the most "stable" parts of the New Testament, and have generally not been questioned by Christians/Christian authorities.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: On several occasions, Paul mentions some of the rituals his Christ followers were performing (e.g., the Lord's supper, baptism) and how they should perform them. These instructions, however, are mostly ad hoc and Paul only mentions them because a specific Christ group needs further instructions or knowledge about a specific rite/ritual.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: Paul sees himself and his co-workers as having authority in the Christ groups they have founded.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Supernatural forces

Notes: By virtue of his calling, Paul is the apostle to the gentiles and therefore has been given authority by the god of Israel over those he has recruited to the Jesus movement.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Even though the Pauline epistles do contain guidance on how Christ followers should live their lives, the epistles do not contain formal legal instructions (like, e.g., Leviticus in the Hebrew Bible)

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: Paul contrasts the spirit with the flesh, where the flesh often is seen as weak and/or acting against God.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: According to Paul, the spirit of a person is not the same thing as that persons body or flesh. These two entities, spirit and body/flesh, are intertwined since the spirit is confined to the body/flesh, but the two can at times be in opposition to each other (with the spirit being viewed as the entity that strives toward the will of God)

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: The body a person has during his/her lifetime is, Paul argues, different from the body that he/she will have at the resurrection. Thus, there are different types of bodies in Paul's mind (cf. 1 Cor 15).

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: There is some evidence in 1 Cor that the audience think of the body as something that is not of central importance, but that one should take care of one's mind more carefully. This seems to have led some of the Corinthian Christ followers to live a life where they acted in sinful ways with their bodies, since they did not think that would be a problem as long as they kept their minds in check.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: After Paul's time, many discussions about the potential dualism of mind-body have arisen. One significant example is gnosticism (which some scholars have tried to trace back to Paul's own time) which display a clear mind-body dualism.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: For Paul, the body one has in this life is different from the body one attains at the resurrection of the dead (cf. 1 Corinthians 15).

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: Paul talks about "heaven" as the place where Christ followers will dwell after the resurrection.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife with God will last forever. In 1 Cor 5:1-10 Paul writes: "For we know that if the earthly tent we live in is destroyed, we have a building from God, a house not made with hands, eternal in the heavens. For in this tent we groan, longing to be clothed with our heavenly dwelling—if indeed, when we have taken it off we will not be found naked. For while we are still in this tent, we groan under our burden, because we wish not to be unclothed but to be further clothed, so that what is mortal may be swallowed up by life. He who has prepared us for this very thing is God, who has given us the Spirit as a guarantee. So we are always confident; even though we know that while we are at home in the body we are away from the Lord—for we walk by faith, not by sight. Yes, we do have confidence, and we would rather be away from the body and at home with the Lord. So whether we are at home or away, we make it our aim to please him. For all of us must appear before the judgment seat of Christ, so that each may receive recompense for what has been done in the body, whether good or evil. (Translation from NRSV.)

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: As with many topics in the Pauline epistles scholars debate exactly how Paul envisioned the afterlife. However, it seems clear that those who are Christ followers will dwell with God and Jesus in "heaven" (but there is no clear definition of how this "heaven" looks like).

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Paul displays a similar belief in the god of Israel that is seen among other Jews before, during, and after his time.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Paul's view of the god of Israel conforms to the believe of Second Temple Judaism and he believes that the god of Israel is the creator of the world and that this god is in control of the universe (but not in the sense that the god controls everything that happens, just that ultimately everything that happens is within God's knowledge)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: God's knowledge of the Christ follower is unrestricted and he has sent his Spirit to the Christ follower to help them pray for what truly matters.

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Paul does not indicate that God would not be able to see or have knowledge of those outside the Christ groups. In fact, in 1 Cor 5:13 Paul says that God will judge those on the outside (i.e., those who are not members of the Christ groups). This indicates that God has knowledge about this group as well.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: In Rom 8:27, Paul writes that God searches the heart of the Christ

followers. Thus, God knows the innermost thoughts of his faithful.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– I don't know

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– I don't know

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– No

Notes: From Paul's point of view, God does not have any "negative" emotions. Paul's God is one that loves his Christ followers, who reciprocate this love. However, God can show anger and other emotions that might be thought of as "negative" (but according to Paul, this anger is justified, cf. Rom 1:18-32).

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Notes: Even though Paul thinks that there are other spiritual beings than the god of Israel, Christ followers must only worship the god of Israel.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Through revelations. It was through a revelation that Paul first came to believe that Jesus from Nazareth was the Messiah (Gal 1:15-16). God's Spirit helps the Christ follower to live according to God's will and those Christ followers who listens to the Spirit will be able to live a life worthy of God. (It's not exactly clear how the Spirit communicates with Christ followers.)

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– I don't know

Notes: Paul invited his Christ followers to worship the god of Israel; however, Paul's epistles as such is not a way of communicating with the high-god

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Paul recognizes several types of non-human spiritual beings, such as angels, demons, gods, and lords. The exact role they play in the world is unclear.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: There are many instances in the Bible where people see supernatural beings. However, Paul does not give many details on how or if Christ followers can see supernatural beings. One example, though, comes from 2 Cor 12, where Paul mentions a person who was taken to the "third heaven" and heard "things that are not to be told," but it is unclear if this person saw Christ or any other supernatural being.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Paul mentions that he has a thorn in the flesh, which he calls a "messenger of satan." Other than this remark, Paul does not go into detail on how the spiritual world can be physically felt.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: It seems like the supernatural beings Paul mentions have some knowledge about this world, but he never goes into any detail about this topic. But it seems safe to assume, based on Paul's Jewish heritage, that he held a more or less traditional Jewish view of supernatural beings, like angels and demons, which means that Paul most likely thought these beings had more knowledge of the world than humans, but that they also were restricted and not all-knowing (like God).

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– I don't know

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: Paul recognizes several types of non-human spiritual beings, such as angels, demons, gods, and lords. The exact role they play in the world is unclear. Moreover, Paul only recognizes one god as the highest god (the god of Israel) and one lord (Jesus Christ) as his own lord.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: Paul writes that Christ followers are to judge angels (1 Cor 6:3). This indicates a kind of hierarchy. Of course, the god of Israel and Lord Jesus Christ are the highest in the supernatural hierarchy (cf. 1 Cor 8:5-6). Within this relationship, God is the one who will ultimately be the highest one (1 Cor 15:24-28).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: In Paul's imagination, several beings are present in the world, e.g., demons and angels.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: God has insight in peoples' lives and is able to see both the outward and inward doings and qualities of humans.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: In 2 Cor 12:17, Paul complains about a "thorn in the flesh" that is related to satan.

↳ Done only by high god

– I don't know

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– I don't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Notes: In 1 Cor 5, Paul tells the Corinthian Christ followers that a member of the group who is living together with his father's wife should be handed "over to Satan for the destruction of the flesh." This is so that his "his spirit may be saved in the day of the Lord" (NRSV).

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: In 1 Cor 5, Paul speaks of a man who is living with his father's wife. In Paul's eyes, this is a grave sin. On the fate of this man, Paul says: "For though absent in body, I am present in spirit; and as if present I have already pronounced judgment in the name of the Lord Jesus on the man who has done such a thing. When you are assembled, and my spirit is present with the power of our Lord Jesus, you are to hand this man over to Satan for the destruction of the flesh, so that his spirit may be saved in the day of the Lord" (1 Cor 5:3-5; NRSV).

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: Those who are adherents of the Jesus movement will gain eternal life with the god of Israel. Those who are not will not.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: Paul mentions that he has been given a "thorn in the flesh" by a messenger of satan. Paul also tells the Galatians that before they came to know the god of Israel, and be known by him, they were enslaved by beings that were not gods by nature (Gal 4:8). This indicates that being under the influence of other spiritual beings was in itself a negative thing and its own punishment. There are many stories outside of the Pauline epistles (e.g, in the Hebrew Bible and the New Testament gospels) on how supernatural beings act in this life. But Paul himself does not say much on the topic.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Even though the god of Israel "takes care" of Christ followers (1 Cor 10:13), this does not mean that Christ followers are automatically rewarded with good things in this life or are not put in difficult or dangerous situation (exemplified by Paul himself who was killed by the Romans).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ died so that those who become his followers can be justified by Christ's death on the cross. Through Christ's death, Paul claims, those who put their faith in Christ are made righteous (Gal 2:21; Rom 5:1-2).

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

Notes: Even though Paul views Jesus of Nazareth as the rightful ruler of this earth and of humanity, he does not envision Jesus to establish a political rule as such.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ is connected with the "religious" life of the Jesus movement, but according to Paul, Jesus's aim was not to restore Judaism; but to bring humanity into a right relationship with God (cf. Rom 5:1-2).

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Questions surrounding eschatology permeate the Pauline epistles and he has to instruct his Christ followers on several occasions with regards to questions about the end time (see esp. 1 Cor 15 and 1 Thess). Paul most likely thought that Jesus would return sometime during his own lifetime. In 1 Cor 1:8 ("He will also strengthen you to the end, so that you may be blameless on the day of our Lord Jesus Christ, NRSV"), Paul indicates that he thinks that those who are Christ follower during his own time will also be alive when Christ comes back. Further, in 1 Cor 10:11 the apostle states that he and his fellow Christ followers are living in the end times.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: Even though Paul thinks that he and other Christ followers are experiencing the end of time, he never suggests a specific time or date when the "final" end will be at.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of new political system

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

Notes: For Paul and his Christ followers, the eschaton is a positive event since this is the point in time when they will see and live with their god forever.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– Yes

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: In various occasions, Paul mentions how Christ followers should and should not behave. The strongest emphasis is on worshiping the god of Israel and not actively participate in non-Jewish cults. For Paul, this is not debatable. Another area Paul mentions is sexual behaviour. In 1 Cor 6:12-20, he tells the Corinthians that they cannot have sexual relations with a prostitute, since the Corinthians' bodies are the temple of the Holy Spirit. The basics for Paul's instructions on social norms, ethics and related things is that the Christ follower has been liberated from being a slave under sin and is now a slave/servant of Christ instead (Rom 6). Moreover, Paul emphasizes the basic instructions found in the Jewish law of living a righteous, loving, and humble life (Gal 5:22-23).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: Paul advises the Galatians that "if anyone is detected in a transgression, you who have received the Spirit should restore such a one in a spirit of gentleness." (Gal 6:1; NRSV). He also advises them to carry each others' burdens. Thus, Paul envisions that members of the Christ groups should take care of one another and show forgiveness when someone makes a mistake.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: Paul mentions a collection that is taking place for the Christ followers in Jerusalem and he expects that Christ followers in other geographical locations (e.g., Corinth) will contribute toward this collection.

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: Paul wants his Christ followers to live a life in righteousness, just like the god of Israel is righteous. The idea of living a righteous life includes many things, such as self-control, proper worship, generosity, love, and faith.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Even though Paul does not expect his gentile Christ followers to adhere to all the purity laws of the Hebrew Bible, he does expect them to not practice sexual immorality, worship other gods than the god of Israel or take part in cultic rituals outside of the Jesus movement. One of the foundations to this is that Paul thinks of the Christ followers as God's temple and as such

they must remain ritually pure for their god.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: For Paul the most important virtue of a Christ follower is that he/she is loyal to the god of Israel and the Lord Jesus Christ. These are the only spiritual beings Christ followers should worship (1 Cor 8:5-6).

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: In 1 Cor 6:1-11, Paul laments the fact that some Christ follower are taking each other to court. Instead, Paul argues, Christ followers should be able to settle these matters among themselves.

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– I don't know

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: At times, Paul mentions both his own trials and those of the Christ followers. However, Paul instills a sense of security among the Christ followers by telling them that God will not let any trial overcome them.

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: In Gal 5:22-23, Paul tells the Galatians that self-control is a fruit of the Spirit and that this is something to strive toward.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Notes: Paul does not generally emphasize status/nobility as something to seek or that it would be good thing in and of itself. It's likely that the members of the Pauline Christ groups did have some economic resources, but only a limited number would have been of higher rank (cf. Erastos in Rom 16:23).

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– I don't know

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: One of the foremost things Paul mentions about hope is the hope/belief that Christ will return. This, Paul says, is worth holding out for since Christ's return will bring about such glory that the sufferings of this present time cannot be compared with it (Rom 8:18).

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Notes: Probably the greatest virtue Paul stresses is the faith/belief that Jesus from Nazareth is God's messiah.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Paul discusses marriage in 1 Cor 7 and tells his audience that if they want to marry, that is fine, and if they want to live celibate, that is fine too.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Paul takes for granted that a "proper" relationship is a marriage between a man and a woman. Paul mentions activities where two people of the same sex have intercourse as something negative. (However, scholars debate whether Paul talks about the modern concept of "homosexuality," where two consenting partners have intercourse, or if he is referring to something else where the sexual act functioned in a way where one part dominated the other and there was no loving relationship behind the sexual act.)

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Paul has a discussion about "food offered to idols" in 1 Cor 8. Even though interpretations vary, it is likely that Paul allows Christ followers to eat such food in principle.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: Paul makes a collection for the Christ group in Jerusalem, but one is by no means required to make a donation to this collection in order to be a member of the Jesus movement.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Paul instructs his Christ followers on how they should act during their meetings and they seem to have met at least once a week (1 Cor 16:2).

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Paul instructs the Christ followers on how they should live in various of his epistles. Not living according to these norms could lead to possible exclusion by Paul and the Christ group.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Christ followers likely met in a variety of places, like households, restaurants, gardens, or hired dining rooms.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Members of Christ groups celebrated a communal meal, labelled the "Lord's supper," and they practiced water immersion, baptism, as initiation rites.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Notes: Paul connects his gentile Christ followers to the lineage of Abraham in order to claim that they, through Christ, now (like Jews) are children of God and participants in the covenant God made with Abraham. This is most notable in Romans and Galatian.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Notes: Paul collects money for the Christ followers in Jerusalem and urges his other Christ groups to donate toward this collection.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– I don't know

Notes: Paul seems to take for granted that members attend the group's meetings.

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The Christ groups Paul addressed are best viewed as ancient associations and cultic groups.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: After the Pauline epistles were written, they likely circulated among different Christ groups. Later, they became important documents for the wider emerging church and they were highly regarded as some of the most important theological documents for the early church and therefore saved and later incorporated in to the New Testament.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: The Pauline epistles do not display any organized way of transferring money or other things to those who are poor or of lower status. However, Paul mentions that Christ followers should help each other out when needed (the collection to the holy ones in Jerusalem is one example of this).

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: The exact educational settings in the early Jesus movement are unclear.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– I don't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Paul assumes that his Christ followers will respect him and not abandon his message/teaching. This is prominent in Galatians.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Pauline Epistles, Thiessen, Matthew. Paul and the Gentile Problem. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

Reference: Pauline Epistles, Fredriksen, Paula. Paul: The Pagans' Apostle. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2017.

Reference: Pauline Epistles, Campbell, Douglas A.. Paul: An Apostle's Journey. Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 2018.

Reference: Pauline Epistles, Sanders, E. P.. Paul: The Apostle's Life, Letters, and Thought. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2015.

Reference: Pauline Epistles, Hooker, Morna D.. Paul: A Short Introduction. Oxford: Oneworld Publications, 2003.

Reference: Pauline Epistles, Boccaccini, Gabriele, and Carlos Segovia. Paul the Jew: Rereading the Apostle as a Figure of Second Temple Judaism. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2016.